

Interaction between climatic conditions, water- and sediment-fluxes in an alpine basin: Long-term monthly and seasonal analysis

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ABSTRACT

Mountain basins are sites where complex interactions among climatic, geological, geomorphic, and ecological conditions can unfold. These interplays can be reflected in the erosion processes, and in the water and sediment fluxes released along the stream network, which can be highly variable in time and space. To investigate the relationships between temperature, precipitation, runoff, and sediment fluxes at monthly and seasonal scales in an Alpine basin, this work analyzed a long-term (January 1987–September 2018) field dataset produced in the Rio Cordon basin (eastern Italian Alps). The monthly variability revealed that higher precipitation occurred in summer (i.e., June–August). However, the runoff peaked in May generated by the snowmelt process. The total sediment load exhibited two peaks in May and September, somewhat reflecting the pattern of the monthly peak of water discharge. The monthly correlation analysis proved that temperature and precipitation weakly influenced the variables investigated, while the peak of water discharge was a good predictor of sediment fluxes observed. At the seasonal scale, temperature influenced snowmelt and summer dynamics, while precipitation showed the highest correlations in autumn. The hysteresis patterns obtained by the relationships between the averaged peak of water discharge and sediment loads (suspended load and bedload) highlighted the succession of high transport efficiency months and months characterized by supply-limited conditions. Such dynamics appeared strongly influenced by a single month, i.e., September 1994, when a large and infrequent flood affected the study basin. September 1994 resulted in a breakpoint in the mass curve built by relating cumulated runoff and cumulated total load, inducing a change in the long-term trend observed until then. Specifically, about 8 years of intensified sediment load were noted, a period during which the Rio Cordon experienced frequent streamed reworking and release of fine material. These findings demonstrated how alpine basins can respond to large and infrequent events, which can be expected more frequently due to climate change, providing important insights into areas such as soil erosion control, river basin management and hazard assessment.

1. Introduction

In the fluvial systems, the complex interaction between climatic conditions, water- and sediment-fluxes can influence the hydrological and erosional processes, with impacts on the geomorphic and ecological settings (Hinderer et al., 2013; Hoffmann et al., 2013; Coviello et al., 2022). This dynamic is particularly evident in the alpine mountain basins, where temperature, precipitations, water discharge, and sediment transport exhibit distinctive conditions (Bocchiola, 2014; Antoniazza et al., 2022). In glacierized basins, temperature and rainfall can strongly control the production of runoff volume (Duethmann et al., 2015) with manifest consequences on sediment fluxes (Lane et al., 2017; Comiti et al., 2019; Carrillo and Mao, 2020). Such relationships were also

documented in the unglacierized basins although they frequently appear more complex (Duvert et al., 2012; Diodato et al., 2018; Tuset et al., 2016). By controlling the weathering processes, the climatic conditions can evidently influence the sediment supply enrichment or depletion in the basin (Bennett et al., 2013; Ariagno et al., 2022). If the sediment is produced in sediment source areas connected to the channel network, it can feed the fluvial sediment transport, which, in mountain basins, acts mainly as suspended sediment and bedload transport (Iida et al., 2012; Mao and Carrillo, 2017; Pitlick et al., 2021). These latter may reveal high partitioning variability both during flood event and over longer time scales. In the Pitzbach catchment, Turowski et al. (2010) observed a predominance of suspended load fraction over the long term with an evident augment of bedload fraction during larger discharges. Analyzing

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about three decades of sediment flux measurements in the Rio Cordon catchment, a long-term bedload fraction equal to 21 % was estimated. However, this fraction increased to 44 % and 89 % at annual- and event-scale, respectively (Rainato et al., 2017). Similarly, a bedload fraction ranging between 27 and 36 % was found by Cienciala et al. (2020) in the Sullivan Creek mountain basin, by analyzing the sediment deposited over a century.

Several authors demonstrated how the transport efficiency expressed by a fluvial system depends not only on the sediment availability but also on the flood magnitude (flood regime) and the relative morphological setting (Bejar et al., 2018; Pellegrini et al., 2023; Savi et al., 2023). Long periods characterized by low-magnitude floods can induce low sediment yield, resulting in sediment accumulation across the basin. This accumulation may then favor abrupt sedimentary responses in case of high hydraulic forcing (López-Tarazón et al., 2010; Rainato et al., 2021). High-magnitude floods can also lead to extensive erosions over the basin and stream network, which may react by boosting the sediment conveyance over the long term (Bathurst and Ashiq, 1998). In the Erlenbach alpine basin, Rickenmann (2020) documented how exceptional flood events triggered a memory effect on the sediment dynamics, by altering the step-pool configuration and increasing the sediment availability. Such conditions resulted in an evident decrease in the bedload critical discharge in the 25 subsequent events. Differently, a large and infrequent flood event largely reshaped the Rio Cordon stream in October 2018, but already in 2020 the annual suspended sediment fluxes resulted to be in line with those observed before the flood (Pellegrini et al., 2023).

An additional factor that can influence the sediment conveyance is the morphological setting of the basin, which can faster or not the transmission of the sediment pulse, depending on the topographic configuration and the relative structural sediment connectivity (Mao et al., 2009; Najafi et al., 2021; Martini et al., 2022). The sediment transport processes can also be affected by the morphological setting of the stream network. In this sense, the mountain streams frequently exhibit a step-pool morphology, i.e., a bedform configuration featuring the alternation of steps composed of keystones as boulders and large cobbles, and pools containing generally finer material. This particular configuration combined with the frequent non-fluvial nature of the keystones (e.g., colluvial processes) means that this morphology can dissipate a large amount of energy during floods, resisting to high-magnitude events (Wilcox et al., 2011; Mao et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2023). However, literature reports several cases of step-pool configuration removal as a consequence of extreme events, thus causing an augment of sediment availability along the stream network and promoting a subsequent increase in transport efficiency (Lenzi et al., 2004; Turowski et al., 2009; Molnar et al., 2010).

Overall, these conditions may result in temporal fluctuations of water- and sediment-fluxes, detectable at the event scale but also over longer periods such as monthly, seasonal, and annual scales (Tuset et al., 2020). Particularly, the temporal variability exhibited by the hydraulic forcing-sediment load relationship can be described through hysteretic cycles, the patterns of which may depend on the antecedent flow and sediment availability conditions, timing of sediment supply, localization of sediment sources and sediment pulses propagation schemes (Yu et al., 2009; Schneider et al., 2016; Rickenmann, 2020; Comiti et al., 2019; Liébault et al., 2022).

In light of this, the relationships between climatic, hydrological and sedimentary conditions resulted highly complex in the alpine environment. A complexity that is further exacerbated by the ongoing climate change that is strongly affecting temperature and precipitation patterns in Alpine basins, where, therefore, sedimentary and morphological responses never observed before may be triggered (Hoffmann et al., 2013; Baewert and Morche, 2014; Bocchiola, 2014; Lane et al., 2017; Pellegrini et al., 2021a). This makes it difficult to sustainably manage mountain basins, and this challenge may increase in the future (Campana et al., 2014; Lane et al., 2017).

This work aims to investigate, in an Alpine basin, the relationships between temperature, precipitation, runoff, and sediment yield at monthly and seasonal scales. To this end, a long-term (January 1987–September 2018) field dataset was used to: (i) analyze the temporal dispersion of the variables investigated, (ii) the correlation between them, (iii) the hysteresis patterns in the relationships between water discharge and sediment loads and (iv) how the sediment dynamics acted during altered basin conditions due to a large and infrequent flood.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study basin

The Rio Cordon catchment (Fig. 1) extends over 5 km² in the Dolomites (eastern Italian Alps). The basin is part of the Southern Limestone Alps with geology dominated by dolomites, sandstones, volcanic conglomerates (Wengen group), and calcareous-marly rocks (Buchenstein group). The basin elevation falls between 1763 and 2763 m a.s.l., leading to an average slope of 27° (Oss Cazzador et al., 2021). About 61 % of the basin area is occupied by alpine grasslands, while shrubs and bare lands cover 18 % and 14 % of the catchment, respectively. The remaining 7 % is covered by spruce and larch forest. In 2016, 420 active sediment source areas were identified in the catchment, affecting about 13 % of the basin area. These source areas consisted mainly of landslides, active talus, erosional areas and, debris flow channels (Oss Cazzador et al., 2020). The Rio Cordon basin is characterized by alpine climate conditions, featuring a mean annual temperature equal to 4.0 °C and a mean annual precipitation of 1180 mm (Pagano et al., 2019; Pellegrini et al., 2023). About 35 % of this precipitation falls as snow (García-Rama, 2017).

The Rio Cordon channel exhibited average-slope and -width equal to 17 % and 5.3 m, respectively (Pellegrini et al., 2021b). This steep configuration is accompanied by a strongly armored streambed with $D_{16}/D_{50}/D_{84}$ of the surface material equal to 29/114/358 mm (Rainato et al., 2018). Such conditions promoted the development of boulder-cascade and step-pool morphologies over the main channel. The bankfull discharge corresponded to 2.30 m³ s⁻¹ (Rainato et al., 2020).

2.2. 1987–2018 monitoring activity

In 1986, a permanent monitoring station was built at the outlet of the Rio Cordon basin to continuously monitor climatic conditions, water discharge, suspended sediment load, and bedload (Fig. 1). This station was designed and realized through a collaboration between Veneto Region and University of Padova, and began to operate at full capacity in 1987 under the management of the ARPA Veneto (Fattorelli et al., 1988; Lenzi et al., 1999; Lenzi and Marchi, 2000; Mao et al., 2010). Specifically, the monitoring station was made at 1763 m a.s.l. recording air temperature (T , in °C) and precipitation (P , in mm) hourly by a temperature sensor and a heated rain gauge, respectively. Climate data were then released on a monthly scale, while from 2010 they were also available on daily and sub-daily scales. Water discharge (Q , in m³ s⁻¹) was measured at three different locations along the monitoring station, by a sharp-crested weir and two water gauges. Coupled with the latter, two turbidimeters were installed to measure the turbidity (in NTU, Nephelometric Turbidity Units). Turbidity was transformed in suspended sediment concentration (SSC, in g l⁻¹) using the turbidity–SSC relationships specifically determined in the Rio Cordon by Lenzi and Marchi (2000). Such equations were based on continuous measurements realized over different flow conditions and different seasons and were largely used to estimate suspended sediment loads in the Rio Cordon (Lenzi and Marchi, 2000; Lenzi et al., 2003; Rainato et al., 2017). Specifically, two rating curves were developed: Eq. 1 was used for turbidity <240 NTU, while the suspension of coarse particles makes it necessary to use Eq. 2 for turbidity >240 NTU.

Fig. 1. (A) Rio Cordon basin, (B) its location within northern Italy, and the corresponding permanent monitoring station viewed from (C) downstream and (D) upstream.

$$SSC = 50.12 (NTU/1000)^{2.46} \quad (1)$$

$$SSC = 22.59 (NTU/1000)^{2.00} + 30.89 (NTU/1000) - 7.05 \quad (2)$$

Both water gauges and turbidimeters were programmed to sample hourly during low flow conditions ($Q < 1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), switching to sampling every 5 min during larger discharge ($Q > 1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). According to the previous analyses realized in the basin (Rainato et al., 2017; Pagano et al., 2019), Q and SSC recorded by the upstream sensors were used for this study. Then, the availability of Q and SSC enabled to compute the suspended sediment load (SSL , in t).

The bedload material ($D > 20 \text{ mm}$) was separated from the water flow by means of an inclined metallic grid and conveyed to a storage area. Here, 24 ultrasonic sensors continuously measured the coarse material accumulation, permitting to determine the bedload transport rate. However, these devices stopped working properly in 2012, year from which a Terrestrial Laser Scanner was used to survey the bedload volume. The finer bedload ($D < 20 \text{ mm}$) was conveyed to a settling basin at the monitoring station outlet, where pressure transducers cells allowed estimation of sediment amount. As with the ultrasonic sensors installed in the storage area, the pressure transducers cells did not work properly over the long term, however, Lenzi and Marchi (2000) demonstrated that the finer bedload during the flood events was transported in suspension and, then, measured by turbidimeters. Also, a large part of the finer bedload was deposited with coarser fraction in the storage area and, computed from the bedload volume measured by the Terrestrial Laser Scanner survey (Rainato et al., 2017). Thus, the bedload volume was transformed in mass (BL , in t) using a coarse material porosity equal to 35 % and a sediment density of 2.65 t m^{-3} . A detailed description of the Rio Cordon permanent monitoring station, including specifications about the devices installed and the data-acquisition and -collection

methods can be found in Rainato et al. (2017).

In September 1994, the Rio Cordon monitoring program permitted to document the effects induced by a large and infrequent flood on the basin. The event was caused by an intense rainfall, which triggered a flash flood and high sediment transport. Such conditions were accompanied by the activation of several sediment source areas in the basin and by the removal of bedforms and armor layer from the Rio Cordon streambed (Rainato et al., 2017). A second large and infrequent flood occurred in October 2018, severely affecting the stream network, damaging most of the installed equipment, and, therefore, interrupting the long-term monitoring program (Pellegrini et al., 2023). Consequently, the latter produced a dataset spanning from January 1987 to September 2018, which was used in the present work. Overall, 33 flood events were recorded and characterized in detail during this period; however, climatic conditions, runoff- and sediment-dynamics acting in the study basin, as well as the relationships between them, were never investigated on a monthly scale and only partially at a seasonal scale (Lenzi et al., 2003; Rainato et al., 2017). This causes understanding of the complex dynamics acting in the Rio Cordon basin to be only partial, while the availability of continuous data over the long term could offer an opportunity to overcome this deficiency. In particular, investigations at monthly and seasonal scales can permit comprehension of dynamics on larger time scales than events, allowing comparison with other long-term instrumented basins. To this end, the data produced by the permanent monitoring station were summed or averaged on a monthly scale, determining for each of the months analyzed the variables described in Table 1.

The effective runoff volume (ER) is understood as the hydrograph volume exceeding the critical discharge for entrainment of coarse streambed material. In the Rio Cordon, such a threshold was estimated by bedload tracing and was found to be equal to $0.44 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Rainato

Table 1
Variables investigated on the monthly scale over the period January 1987–September 2018 and their descriptive statistics.

Acronym	Variable (unit of measurement)	Min	Max	Mean	Std. dev.
T_{Avg}	Average air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-7.0	17.2	5.2	6.4
P_{Tot}	Total precipitation (mm)	0.0	386.0	98.8	70.4
Q_{Mean}	Mean water discharge ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	0.03	1.57	0.30	0.21
Q_{Peak}	Peak of water discharge ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	0.05	10.42	0.94	1.13
Ru	Total runoff volume (m^3)	482	2,939,685	663,396	490,275
ER	Effective runoff volume (m^3)	1595	2,729,434	495,697	563,824
SSC_{Avg}	Average suspended sediment concentration (g l^{-1})	0.001	0.801	0.028	0.064
SSC_{Peak}	Peak of suspended sediment concentration (g l^{-1})	0.005	48,900	0.946	4.087
SSL	Suspended sediment load (t)	0.1	3161.9	64.9	265.6
BL	Bedload (t)	0.0	1541.7	17.6	121.0
TL	Total sediment load (t)	0.1	4703.6	82.7	380.7

et al., 2020). To better understand the dynamics acting in the study basin, the variables reported in Table 1 were also investigated at the seasonal scale. In this sense, the meteorological seasons were analyzed, and, therefore, winter, spring, summer, and autumn were intended as the periods December–February, March–May, June–August, and September–November, respectively.

Correlation matrix and regression analysis were used to determine the relationships between the variables analyzed at monthly and seasonal scales. The significance of such relationships was tested through Pearson correlation coefficient (r), coefficient of determination (R^2), and p-value. The double mass curve method was used to estimate the long-term consistency between specific variables. This approach permits

the description of temporal trends and associated changing points, as these induce variations in the linear regression slopes (Zhang et al., 2023). Particularly, in the Rio Cordon, the double mass curve was used to analyze the long-term trend exhibited by the cumulated runoff and cumulated total load relationship, testing for any changes.

3. Results

3.1. Monthly variability

Over the study period, the monthly variables showed a marked variability. T_{Avg} gradually increased during the spring, peaking in July in

Fig. 2. Box plots of (A) monthly average air temperature, (B) monthly total precipitation, (C) monthly total runoff volume, (D) monthly peak of water discharge, (E) monthly peak of suspended sediment concentration, (F) monthly total sediment load. No suspended sediment load or bedload transport was recorded in December, January, February and March. The black horizontal line indicates the median value, while the black cross identifies the mean value. The box indicates the interquartile range, while the whiskers represent the values included within 1.5 times the interquartile range. Dots indicates the outlier values. Box plots of Q_{Mean} , ER , SSC_{Avg} , SSL , and BL were reported in the Supplementary material, Fig. 1. The color scales represent the four seasons analyzed, i.e., gray-scale for winter, green-scale for spring, yellow-red-scale for summer, and blue-scale for autumn.

both mean (14.0 °C) and median (14.5 °C) terms, while the lowest average air temperature (−2.3 °C) was measured in December (Fig. 2A). Compared with T_{Avg} , the monthly P_{Tot} exhibited a larger inter-annual variability with several outliers and frequent means higher than medians (Fig. 2B). In mean terms, January showed the lowest total precipitation (43.1 mm), which increased during the spring and, then, remained steadily >100 mm during May–November. In this sense, the largest mean P_{Tot} was observed in July (142.1 mm). However, a pronounced variability was measured in May ($P_{Tot} > 200.0$ mm) and, especially, in October and November with monthly total precipitation >350.0 mm, representing the highest P_{Tot} recorded during the study period. Total runoff volume (Ru) did not reflect the pattern expressed by P_{Tot} . In fact, Ru remained quite low between January and early spring, increasing abruptly in May, when both the highest mean ($1.35 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$) and median ($1.36 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$) values were observed. Starting from June, the total runoff volume constantly decreased over the months, showing a

pronounced inter-annual variability in autumn (Fig. 2C). A comparable trend can be observed in the monthly variability expressed by Q_{Mean} and ER (Supplementary material, Fig. 1). In terms of mean values, the distribution of Q_{Peak} (Fig. 2D) exhibited an increase starting from January with a first peak in May ($1.31 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) followed by a general decrease over the summer and a second peak in October ($1.38 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The May peak can also be noted in the median values, which then gradually decreased until December (Fig. 2D). Since June, the inter-annual variability clearly increased, becoming particularly evident in autumn. In September, Q_{Peak} spanned over about two orders of magnitude, while in October and November, the means were clearly higher than medians. Differently from SSC_{Avg} (Supplementary material, Fig. 1), a manifest variability can be noted in the analysis of SSC_{Peak} , which distribution was characterized by a large presence of outliers (Fig. 2E). However, the mean and, especially, median values showed a certain stability over the months. The median SSC_{Peak} ranged between 0.03 g l^{-1} in September

Fig. 3. Distribution of monthly relative amounts in terms of total precipitation (P_{Tot}), total runoff volume (Ru), suspended sediment load (SSL), and bedload (BL) over the study period (January 1987–September 2018). No suspended sediment load or bedload transport was recorded in December, January, February and March. The color scales represent the four seasons analyzed, i.e., gray-scale for winter, green-scale for spring, yellow-red-scale for summer, and blue-scale for autumn.

and November to 0.10 g l^{-1} in May and July. Instead, the mean SSC_{Peak} spanned from 0.42 g l^{-1} in June to 1.90 g l^{-1} in September. The distribution of the total sediment load expressed the integration of the trends shown by SSL and BL (Supplementary material, Fig. 1) with an evident inter-annual variability and manifest differences between mean and median monthly values (Fig. 2F). Similarly to Q_{Peak} , two peaks were observed in terms of mean TL . The first peak in May (141.9 t) was followed by a decrease in summer and, then, by the second peak in September (184.3 t). Between December and March, neither suspended sediment load nor bedload was recorded (Fig. 2).

Focusing on the cumulated P_{Tot} , Ru , SSL , and BL , the analysis of monthly relative amounts was produced (Fig. 3). The results stressed how P_{Tot} was well spread over the months, with relative amounts ranging from 3.6 % in January to 12.0 % in July. A certain distribution was observed also in terms of Ru . In this case, the winter months accounted only for 1.4 %, while May was the month that expressed the largest Ru contribution (22.3 %). As somewhat noted in the monthly variability analysis, from June onwards Ru gradually decreased, passing from a monthly contribution equal to 18.0 % in June to 6.7 % and 0.9 % in November and December, respectively (Fig. 3). Seasonally, spring (29.2 %) released a runoff lower than summer, which produced the 42.3 % of Ru recorded. Such an amount exceeded even that observed in autumn (27.0 %). SSL and even more markedly BL showed a distribution of relative amounts concentrated in a few months (Fig. 3). In terms of SSL , May and September expressed 25.0 % and 27.7 % of monthly contribution, respectively. Remarkable also was the relative amount of October equal to 16.5 %, highlighting how over 69.0 % of SSL was released in these three months. Seasonally, autumn (51.5 %) exhibited a SSL contribution almost double that expressed by both spring (27.0 %) and summer (21.5 %). BL revealed a marked polarization in the relative amounts (Fig. 3). The main contribution occurred in September (47.9 %) and October (25.1 %). Consequently, autumn released overall 78.3 % of coarse material recorded in the period January 1987–September 2018. Spring (10.3 %) and summer (11.4 %) delivered quite similar relative amounts.

3.2. Relationships between climatic, hydrological and sedimentary conditions on a monthly scale

The correlation matrix (Table 2) highlighted that, at a monthly scale, T_{Avg} was significantly correlated with P_{Tot} and Ru , while no influence was exerted on the water discharge and sediment-concentration or -load. P_{Tot} exhibited a significant relationship with Q_{Mean} , Q_{Peak} , Ru , and SSC_{Peak} . Interestingly, the monthly total precipitation was not related to ER and variables related to sediment load. Q_{Mean} showed a generally high performance in describing the variables investigated. In addition to P_{Tot} , it resulted significantly correlated with Q_{Peak} , Ru , ER , and, remarkably, with SSC_{Peak} , SSL , BL , and TL (Table 2). Similar results were observed for Q_{Peak} but with lower correlation coefficients with Ru and ER , while the correlation was higher with SSC_{Peak} and sediment loads.

Table 2

Correlation matrix between the variables investigated on the monthly scale (Table 1). The values indicate the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), while bold was used in the case of statistical significance (i.e., p -value < 0.01).

	T_{Avg}	P_{Tot}	Q_{Mean}	Q_{Peak}	Ru	ER	SSC_{Avg}	SSC_{Peak}	SSL	BL	TL
T_{Avg}	1.000										
P_{Tot}	0.378	1.000									
Q_{Mean}	0.167	0.314	1.000								
Q_{Peak}	0.124	0.453	0.673	1.000							
Ru	0.237	0.348	0.846	0.530	1.000						
ER	-0.151	0.154	0.886	0.445	0.928	1.000					
SSC_{Avg}	-0.055	-0.021	0.143	-0.009	0.073	0.063	1.000				
SSC_{Peak}	-0.013	0.198	0.458	0.683	0.231	0.249	0.158	1.000			
SSL	0.006	0.170	0.501	0.696	0.265	0.290	0.018	0.853	1.000		
BL	0.103	0.100	0.550	0.820	0.140	0.186	0.184	0.931	0.928	1.000	
TL	0.007	0.175	0.498	0.710	0.261	0.289	0.001	0.882	0.993	0.965	1.000

These latter were also well described by Ru and ER but through r constantly <0.300 (Table 2). Notably, SSC_{Avg} showed no significant correlation with any of the hydrological variables analyzed. Such variables, by contrast, were found to be well related to SSC_{Peak} , with the strongest correlation exhibited by Q_{Peak} ($r = 0.683$). Also, the peak of suspended sediment concentration appeared strongly correlated with SSL , BL , and TL (Table 2). Overall, the sediment loads were not significantly influenced by P_{Tot} during the study period, an influence that was instead exerted by runoff (Ru and ER) and even more by water discharge (Q_{Mean} and Q_{Peak}).

3.3. Relationships between climatic, hydrological and sedimentary conditions on a seasonal scale

Table 3 shows the correlations between winter T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} and variables recorded in spring. The winter average air temperature and the total precipitation weakly influenced the spring variables. Significant correlations were observed only between winter and spring air temperature, and, interestingly, between spring Ru and winter T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} . On the one hand, spring total runoff volume decreased increasing the winter average air temperature, on the other hand, it increased with higher winter P_{Tot} values. The correlation matrix based on the spring months only (Supplementary material, Table 1) highlighted that in this season T_{Avg} was positively correlated with Q_{Mean} , Q_{Peak} , and Ru . A positive correlation was observed also between P_{Tot} and Q_{Peak} , and Ru . Interestingly, no climatic or hydrological variables were found to be correlated with sediment concentrations and loads. In summer (Supplementary material, Table 2), T_{Avg} was negatively correlated with P_{Tot} , Q_{Mean} , Ru , and ER , while P_{Tot} resulted significantly related only to Ru . Differently from the spring season, the hydrological variables of the summer were significantly correlated with sediment loads although with correlation coefficients <0.650. In autumn, T_{Avg} influenced none of the variables investigated, an influence instead provided by P_{Tot} as demonstrated by the positive correlations with Q_{Mean} , Q_{Peak} , Ru , and ER (Supplementary material, Table 3). In the fall season, the hydrological variables exhibited the highest correlations with sediment concentration and loads. Also, SSC_{Peak} was strongly correlated with SSL , BL , and TL . Interestingly, in spring, summer, and autumn, SSL and BL were significantly correlated with r ranging between 0.648 and 0.980.

Focusing on the months in which both BL and SSL were recorded, it is possible to note that a different sediment dynamic occurred across the seasons. In autumn (September–November), the largest loads were mobilized, however, summer (June–August) and autumn plotted similarly in the power law relationship BL - SSL (Fig. 4). Both expressed a statistically significant regression (p -value < 0.01) with comparable coefficient a (6.5 and 6.7), exponent b (0.80 and 0.81) and, therefore, slope. In spring (March–May), the BL - SSL relationship remained statistically significant even if with a more scattered pattern (p -value < 0.05). Particularly, spring settled above the summer and autumn relationships, suggesting that at the same BL , larger SSL were mobilized between

Table 3

Correlation between winter T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} (in rows) and the spring variables (in columns). The values indicate the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), while bold was used in the case of statistical significance (i.e., p -value < 0.01).

	T_{Avg}	P_{Tot}	Q_{Mean}	Q_{Peak}	Ru	ER	SSC_{Avg}	SSC_{Peak}	SSL	BL	TL
T_{Avg}	0.477	-0.277	-0.245	-0.357	-0.529	-0.420	-0.308	-0.210	0.056	0.161	0.000
P_{Tot}	-0.401	0.086	0.369	0.244	0.466	0.391	0.185	-0.165	0.183	-0.391	0.145

Fig. 4. Relationship between suspended sediment load (SSL) and bedload (BL) in the spring ($n = 11$), summer ($n = 8$) and autumn ($n = 13$) months in which both types of sediment transport occurred. Winter has no shown such a condition. The solid lines are the respective best-fit lines (power law regression), of which equations, R^2 , and p -value are reported.

March and May (Fig. 4). Also, it is worth noting that spring exhibited a flatter regression line (exponent $b = 0.45$) respect to summer and autumn fit lines. In winter, no month featured both SSL and BL .

3.4. Hysteresis pattern

The correlation observed between the peak of water discharge and sediment loads enabled to investigate the hysteresis patterns exhibited at a monthly scale by these relationships. Both the variation of monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} with monthly-averaged SSL (Fig. 5A) as well as the variation of monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} with monthly-averaged BL (Fig. 5B) expressed a clockwise hysteresis pattern. Specifically, the relationship

average Q_{Peak} - average SSL showed two consecutive clockwise loops due to a strong increase of both Q_{Peak} and SSL in May, followed by an evident decrease of suspended sediment load in the summer season (June–August). Then, the hysteresis pattern exhibited a second peak in September, when the averaged SSL more than doubled compared to the summer. This is despite an almost stable average peak of water discharge, suggesting the occurrence of high transport efficiency in September. In October, the averaged Q_{Peak} increased to its maximum observed ($1.38 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) but this was not accompanied by an augment in terms of SSL that, instead, exhibited a value lower than both May and September (Fig. 5A). Autumn ended with November, which featured averaged Q_{Peak} and averaged SSL in line to what noted in the summer

Fig. 5. Hysteresis patterns shown by the relationships (A) monthly average peak of water discharge vs. monthly suspended sediment load and (B) monthly average peak of water discharge vs. monthly bedload. The color scales represent the four seasons analyzed, i.e., gray-scale for winter, green-scale for spring, yellow-red-scale for summer, and blue-scale for autumn.

period.

The clockwise pattern expressed by the relationship between monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} and monthly-averaged BL (Fig. 5B) was due to a large discharge with low bedload in May, then, followed by a reduction in both values during the summer season. Particularly, between June and August the average BL was constantly <10 t. Differently, September exhibited very high transport efficiency, with a mean Q_{Peak} comparable to summer but with an average BL about one order of magnitude higher (58.3 t). In October, the average Q_{Peak} increased to the largest observed value ($1.38 m^3 s^{-1}$), which caused the release of an average BL equal to 31.7 t. Finally, November was characterized by an evident decrease both in terms of the peak of water discharge and bedload, reaching values comparable to those observed in summer.

3.5. Sediment dynamics under changed basin conditions

The predominance of September in terms of SSL and BL amounts (Figs. 3, 5) seems to be supported even by the double mass curve analysis realized comparing cumulated Ru and cumulated TL (Fig. 6). Such a relationship experienced in September 1994 an abrupt increase of cumulated TL , producing an evident changing point in the observed long-term trend (Fig. 6). The change was also evident in the regression equations describing the relationships between Ru and TL cumulated values. Particularly, the linear regression built on the pre-September 1994 period (i.e., January 1987–August 1994) exhibited a slope equal to 61.2 (Fig. 6). Starting in September 1994 and up to December 2002, the cumulated Ru –cumulated TL relationship settles on a clearly steeper slope (157.4). Then, in January 2003, a second changing point occurred, consisting of a TL reduction over the subsequent period and causing that corresponding regression plots with a gentler slope (44.6), i.e., a gradient close to that noted in the period before September 1994. Notably, all the computed linear regressions resulted statistically significant (p-value < 0.01) with R^2 spanning between 0.711 and 0.932 (Fig. 6). Also, the ANOVA analysis confirmed that both regressions computed over the periods January 1987–August 1994 and January 2003–September 2018 were statistically different in terms of both

Fig. 6. Double mass curve relating cumulated Ru and cumulated TL over the study period. The white, yellow, and gray dots describe the periods January 1987–August 1994, September 1994–December 2002, and January 2003–September 2018, respectively. The solid lines are the respective linear regression lines, whose equations and R^2 are listed.

intercept (p-value < 0.01) and slope (p-value < 0.01) from that describing the September 1994–December 2002 period.

Focusing on the months in which both BL and SSL occurred, it is interesting to note that the period September 1994–December 2002 also distinguishes itself by an evident correlation between monthly BL and monthly SSC_{Peak} (Table 4). These variables scaled linearly ($R^2 = 0.889$, p-value < 0.01), suggesting that the peak of suspended sediment

Table 4

Parameters of linear regression models relative to the SSC_{Peak} - BL relationship observed in the periods January 1987–August 1994, September 1994–December 2002, and January 2003–September 2018.

Period	N	Slope	Intercept	R ²	p-Value
January 1987–August 1994	6	0.004	0.786	0.021	0.784
September 1994–December 2002	11	0.029	1.403	0.889	0.003
January 2003–September 2018	13	0.038	0.784	0.177	0.153

concentration increased with increasing the bedload amount. As reported in Table 4, the monthly BL -monthly SSC_{Peak} relationship assumed statistical significance only in the period September 1994–December 2002, and not in January 1987–August 1994 or

January 2003–September 2018. Focusing on the BL - SSC_{Peak} relationship computed for the period September 1994–December 2002, no kind of monthly clustering pattern was observed (Fig. 7).

4. Discussion

4.1. Interaction between climatic, hydrological and sedimentary variables

The analysis of air temperature and precipitation amount confirmed that the Rio Cordon basin is characterized by typical alpine climatic conditions, with the highest temperature and precipitations concentrated in the summer months (Brighenti et al., 2021). Despite the generally lower precipitation than the summer months, in May the highest average Ru and the second largest average Q_{Peak} were recorded.

Fig. 7. Relationship between monthly bedload (BL) and monthly peak of suspended sediment concentration (SSC_{Peak}) in the period September 1994–December 2002. The dots are colored accordingly with the occurrence month. Note that data are plotted with log-log scales.

This evident runoff not related, however, to a concomitant increase in precipitation seems to suggest that, in May, the snowmelt played a key role. Particularly, March (mean $T_{Avg} = 0.8$ °C) and April (mean $T_{Avg} = 3.9$ °C) already induced a slight increase in both Ru and Q_{Peak} but the snowmelt contribution seems to have been mainly triggered by May (mean $T_{Avg} = 8.4$ °C). In this sense, the investigation of the relationships between winter climatic conditions and spring variables found that winter T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} influenced the spring Ru (Table 3). The negative correlation between winter average air temperature and spring total runoff volume seems to suggest that high winter temperature promoted snowmelt as early as the winter months, thus reducing the snowpack available to feed spring runoff. The pivotal role of the snowpack was somewhat confirmed also by the positive correlation between winter P_{Tot} and spring Ru , emphasizing that high winter precipitation (i.e., snowfall) caused large spring runoff. Interestingly, these findings agree with the results obtained by Lana-Renault et al. (2011) in the Izas basin (Central Spanish Pyrenees), where the authors detected a marked influence of winter snow accumulation and subsequent melting processes in the runoff production. In the Rio Cordon, the higher monthly Ru (i.e., $>2 \times 10^6$ m³) observed in May could also be explained by the occurrence of rain-on-snow events, which can induce frequent floods in the basin (Lenzi et al., 2003; Rainato et al., 2018). The snowmelt contribution seems to be mainly exhausted in May since from this month onward Ru progressively decreased, stabilizing at an average $Ru \sim 0.5 \times 10^6$ m³ between August and November (Fig. 2). However, the autumn period showed many outliers, highlighting the occurrence of monthly $Ru > 1.0 \times 10^6$ m³. Such a result appears to be in line with the pronounced inter-annual variability observed in autumn P_{Tot} (Fig. 2). This variability resulted also in terms of Q_{Peak} that expressed large ranges in September and, especially, in October–November. Therefore, these findings seem to suggest the occurrence in autumn of large P_{Tot} able to trigger large runoff (i.e., Ru and Q_{Peak}). The large and infrequent floods documented in the Rio Cordon basin in September 1994 and October 2018 seem to support this hypothesis (Rainato et al., 2017; Pellegrini et al., 2023). Interestingly, Q_{Peak} exhibited two peaks in May and October, respectively. Despite the high P_{Tot} , summer months expressed lower mean Q_{Peak} , suggesting a minor efficiency in producing large discharge peaks. Particularly, the P_{Tot} increase observed between May and July was not converted into an increase in either Ru or Q_{Peak} , which on the contrary decreased over the period. This dynamic seems to suggest that between May and June, there was, in hydrological terms, a considerable emptying of the basin and that the abundant summer precipitation also served to recharge the catchment. In this sense, the impact of summer precipitation may also have been limited by the high temperatures recorded between June and August (11.9 °C $<$ mean T_{Avg} $<$ 14.0 °C), which may have promoted high evapotranspiration. However, these hypotheses would deserve a deeper hydrological investigation, possibly based on the use of natural tracers such as electrical conductivity, stable isotopes, water- and soil-temperature (Engel et al., 2016; Michelon et al., 2023). Focusing on the sediment dynamics, winter months were characterized by the absence of sediment fluxes. Such winter inactivity was likely due to particular seasonal conditions such as low air temperature, mainly snowy precipitation, extensive snow cover, and very low runoff, i.e., circumstances preventing the sediment conveyance. In the remaining months, TL showed large inter-annual variability, expressing fluctuations in both mean and median values. Particularly, in the total sediment load two peaks were detected, respectively, in May and October, i.e., a trend somewhat reminiscent of what was observed in Q_{Peak} . Therefore, the monthly variability analysis stressed that summer experienced the largest P_{Tot} but not the highest Q_{Peak} and TL . This was evident also in the analysis of SSL and BL monthly relative amounts, in which summer contributed overall by only 21.4 % and 11.5 %, respectively (Fig. 3). Thus, on a monthly scale, P_{Tot} seems not to have been the best predictor of runoff- and sediment-dynamics. Table 2 proved that T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} had limited influence on the hydrological and sedimentary variables investigated. In particular, the monthly precipitation

expressed significant but highly scattered correlations only with Ru , Q_{Mean} , Q_{Peak} , and SSC_{Peak} (Table 2). However, the picture changes by analyzing the different seasons. In spring, P_{Tot} resulted positively correlated with both Q_{Peak} and Ru and, as expected for the snowmelt period, Q_{Mean} , Q_{Peak} and Ru augmented increasing T_{Avg} (Supplementary material, Table 1). Notably, no significant relationship was observed between climatic or hydrological variables and sediment-concentration or -load, suggesting that in spring the sediment transport was not controlled by climatic or hydraulic forcing but likely by factors related to sediment availability and supply. Interestingly, the influence of T_{Avg} completely changed in summer, when its increase led to the decrease of several hydrological variables, i.e., Q_{Mean} , Ru , and ER (Supplementary material, Table 2). Also, P_{Tot} had no significant influence on any investigated variables, except Ru . Such dynamic could be ascribed to the aforementioned evapotranspiration processes, the hydrological emptying of the basin, and the features of summer rainfall, typically short and intense. In the mountain basin, summer rainfall can trigger large floods (Shakti et al., 2017) but in the Rio Cordon basin seems to be unable to hydrologically and sedimentologically reactivate the catchment. Autumn exhibited interactions different from those observed in spring and summer. T_{Avg} presented no significant correlations, while P_{Tot} appeared well correlated with the hydrological variables, which in turn exhibited highly significant correlations with both sediment-concentrations and -loads (Supplementary material, Table 3). This evident cause-effect relationship between precipitation, runoff, and sediment transport could be explained by the nature of autumn alpine precipitation, i.e., long and persistent rainfall that in the Rio Cordon basin resulted in an efficient rainfall-runoff transformation and, then, an effective sediment transport. In the Vallon de Nant basin (Western Swiss Alps), Antoniazza et al. (2022) documented the decorrelation between air temperature, precipitation, and bedload, motivating it with temporary hydrologic storage in basin compartments such as ground and snowpack. Differently, in the Saldur glacierized basin (Eastern Italian Alps), the sediment fluxes resulted tightly related to summer air temperature, while no significant correlation was observed with rainfall (Comiti et al., 2019). A correlation between annual sediment export and over-threshold rainfall intensity was instead observed by Ariagno et al. (2022) in the Laval basin. In this regard, it should be stressed that an investigation of rainfall intensity is lacking in the Rio Cordon due to the limited availability of such data (i.e., only from 2010). This makes our understanding of the role of the precipitation on hydrological and sedimentary dynamics only partial and limited to cumulated values and not to intensities that occurred, which can strongly influence water- and sediment-fluxes in mountain basins (Mathys et al., 2005; Cuomo et al., 2015). Monthly Q_{Peak} appeared as the main hydrological driver of sediment fluxes measured at a monthly scale (i.e., SSC_{Peak} , BL , SSL , and TL). In literature, the importance of peak of water discharge in describing sediment transport was recognized at different spatial and temporal scales (Schmidt and Morche, 2006; Mao et al., 2009; Duvert et al., 2012; Navratil et al., 2012; Reisenbüchler et al., 2021). In the Rio Cordon, the peak of water discharge already resulted in the largely dominant driver at the event scale, both in terms of sediment mobility as well as in terms of bedload and suspended sediment load (Rainato et al., 2017; Rainato et al., 2020). However, it is interesting to note that the analysis of flood events occurred in the Rio Cordon basin between 2020 and 2021, i.e., two and three years after the large October 2018 flood, revealed different dynamics, identifying the main drivers of suspended sediment transport in the average intensity and total amount of precipitation (Pellegrini et al., 2023). The monthly SSC_{Peak} also exhibited a positive correlation with monthly Q_{Peak} and, notably, it appeared highly correlated with monthly SSL and BL . This relationship between suspended sediment concentration and sediment loads agrees with what was observed at the event scale by Duvert et al. (2012) in small mountain basins and by Misset et al. (2019) in over 50 gravel-bed rivers.

4.2. Hysteresis analysis

The hysteresis pattern analysis reported a clockwise loop in the relationship between monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} and monthly-averaged SSL (Fig. 5A). Particularly, a first peak was noted in May, when a high average Q_{Peak} was accompanied by a large average SSL . In the Rio Cordon basin, this condition echoes the concept of dynamic equilibrium (sensu Lane, 1955), in which high water discharge produced by snowmelt was largely supplied by fine material likely generated during winter by frost weathering and freeze-thaw processes. Summer showed a reduction in both average Q_{Peak} and average SSL . Whether the low water discharges could be explained by a reduced rainfall-runoff transformation efficiency, the poor summer suspended sediment loads could be related to the large conveyance observed in May that may have depleted the sediment availability (Nistor and Church, 2005). The second peak detected in September clearly stressed high transport efficiency in this month, with an average Q_{Peak} comparable to summer ones but with an average SSL more than two times larger. Such transport efficiency can be mainly ascribed to September 1994, when $Q_{Peak} = 10.4 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $SSL = 3162 \text{ t}$ were measured. This result confirmed the impact of the September 1994 flood on the basin, i.e., an impact detectable over the long term not only at the event scale but also at the monthly scale. However, it also suggests another hypothesis, which is that September's efficiency may have been fostered by a summer phase of quiescence and likely sediment replenishment. Nevertheless, this hypothesis will need further investigation such as a more detailed analysis of the summer sediment dynamics. Similarly to May, September seems to induce a certain depletion in sediment availability terms, as suggested by the supply-limited conditions observed in October, when the highest average Q_{Peak} produced an average SSL lower than May and September. Under such conditions, the transport capacity exceeded the sediment supply, promoting erosion along the stream network and, thus, recharging it with fine material (Simon and Rinaldi, 2006; Llana et al., 2024). This replenishment phase seems to provide the conditions for the dynamic equilibrium noted in May. Such a dynamic agrees with the $SSL-BL$ relationship (Fig. 4) that, for the same BL , showed higher SSL in spring than in summer and autumn, emphasizing a larger availability of fine material. A clockwise loop characterized the relationship between monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} and monthly-averaged BL (Fig. 5B). However, differing from what was observed in the relationship between monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} and monthly-averaged SSL (Fig. 5A), in bedload terms, May expressed extremely limited supply conditions. This stressed a mismatch between suspended sediment and bedload dynamics with winter weathering processes supplying the former but not the latter. Interestingly, this diverse effect of the weathering processes was reported also in the Araguás basin (Central Spanish Pyrenees) by Nadal-Romero et al. (2012), who documented a sediment budget dominated by spring suspended load favored, in turn, by a large availability of fine material derived by winter freezing-thawing and wetting-drying processes. In the Rio Cordon, summer resulted in a season of low transmission of coarse material ($BL < 10 \text{ t}$) followed by a transport efficiency increase in September. Therefore, also in terms of BL , the September 1994 ($BL = 1542 \text{ t}$) imposed a wide signal detectable over the long term even on a monthly scale. In this sense, the low coarse sediment fluxes recorded in summer may have somehow favored September's efficiency but, as with SSL , this hypothesis would require further investigations particularly focused on the summer sediment dynamics. Coherently with SSL , October expressed supply-limited conditions, followed by a decrease of both Q_{Peak} and BL in November. In mountain basins, the analysis of hysteresis patterns at monthly or seasonal scales is scarce. Anticlockwise seasonal hysteresis was documented in the Saldur basin as a consequence of the delayed (summer) release of sediment from glacial- and pro-glacial areas (Comiti et al., 2019). Liébault et al. (2022) proved that seasonal anticlockwise loops can be induced also by geomorphic stream conditions. In the Moulin basin (Southern French Prealps), the authors noted low bedload transport efficiency in spring and early

summer due to the storage of loose debris, produced by frost cracking in winter, and aggradation over the main stream. This material was then conveyed downstream in autumn when aggradation ended and the main stream incised into the alluvial material. Hysteresis loops may also be due to the rainfall characteristics as reported in the Laval basin by Ariagno et al. (2022). In this basin, low rainfall intensities favored transport-limited conditions during late spring and early summer, producing an initial anticlockwise loop. Then, the June high-intensity storms caused large sediment export, exhausting the basin and inducing supply-limited conditions in late summer and autumn, i.e., conditions described by a clockwise loop in the second part of the year. Overall, these results and what was observed in the Rio Cordon supported the assumption that mountain basins expressed cyclic patterns, consisting of supply-limited phases followed by pulses of colluvial or alluvial material (Recking, 2012). In particular, the clockwise patterns observed in the Rio Cordon seem to find more explanation in a spring depletion accompanied by an early flushing of readily available material (Nanson, 1974) than in the location of specific sediment sources (Schneider et al., 2016; Rickenmann, 2018). Added to this, there is an autumn peak primarily imposed by the September 1994 event, the magnitude of which also reverberates on a monthly scale.

4.3. Effect of a large and infrequent flood

The impact of the September 1994 flood was clearly proved by the double mass curve analysis, inducing an evident changing point in the long-term trend of cumulated Ru -cumulated TL relationship (Fig. 6). The double mass curve was largely used to assess the long-term consistency between climatic, hydrological and sedimentary variables, permitting to identify the trend changes and the corresponding break-points (Bian et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2020; Bathurst et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). In the Rio Cordon, the September 1994 changing point caused an evident increase in the linear regression slope, which was augmented by a factor of 2.6 compared with the previous period (January 1987–August 1994). Such condition of intensified sediment conveyance lasted until December 2002, thus persisting for over 8 years. Interestingly, the duration of this enhanced monthly sediment delivery resulted consistent with the memory effect observed at the event scale by Rainato et al. (2017). In particular, the authors documented an increase in flood transport efficiency for about a decade, relating it to the wide activation induced by the September 1994 event on the sediment source areas. Other authors reported sediment fluxes intensification after large floods in mountain basins, attributing them to streambed destabilization, triggering of sediment sources and, therefore, to an augmented sediment availability (Turowski et al., 2009; Yager et al., 2012; Masteller et al., 2019; Brenna and Surian, 2023; Rickenmann, 2024). In the period January 2003–September 2018, the cumulated Ru -cumulated TL relationship returned to a regression slope similar to that characterizing the period January 1987–August 1994, suggesting the exhaustion of increased sediment availability. September 1994–December 2002 period was also distinguished by an evident correlation between monthly BL and monthly SSC_{Peak} (Fig. 7). The increase of suspended sediment concentration with increasing bedload amount seems to suggest that the mobilization of streambed material somehow induced an augmented availability of fine sediment. This draws the hypothesis that suspended sediment fluxes during the period September 1994–December 2002 were primarily supplied by in-channel material. Several authors (Estrany et al., 2011; Buendia et al., 2016) demonstrated that streambed can storage large amount of fine material, which is then released consequently to floods large enough to induce streambed reworking. In the Rio Cordon, the relationship between monthly BL and monthly SSC_{Peak} demonstrated that in mountain streams, can occur an interaction between suspended sediment transport and streambed conditions. After collecting 2400 field measurements in 56 gravel bed rivers, Misset et al. (2019) computed an empirical relation between suspended sediment concentration and dimensionless bedload rate.

Such equations were successfully applied to describe suspended sediment fluxes measured during large floods in alpine gravel bed rivers, while its performance decreased if applied to steep, narrow, and armored headwater streams. The $BL - SSC_{Peak}$ correlation observed in the Rio Cordon is then likely to be referred to the altered conditions expressed by streambeds during the September 1994–December 2002 period. In fact, September 1994 caused the removal of the step-pool configuration and the armor layer suppression, making available a large amount of in-channel loose material (Lenzi, 2001; Comiti et al., 2005). Such conditions promoted the streambeds as the main source of fine sediment, even in light of the topographically imposed disconnection of upstream source areas (Martini et al., 2022). This hypothesis agrees with Park and Hunt (2017), who analyzing 38 gravel bed rivers, observed that fine particles release was associated with bedload transport. Consequently, the authors proposed a conceptual model according to which fine particles accumulate in the streambed during a period of armor layer, to be washed with streambed material when the armoring was broken.

5. Conclusion

The analysis of the dataset produced by the Rio Cordon long-term monitoring program stressed that, at a monthly scale, T_{Avg} and P_{Tot} had limited influence on the runoff- and sedimentary-dynamics observed. The climatic conditions appeared to exert a larger influence at the seasonal scale, in particular, influencing hydrological and sedimentary variables in spring, summer, and, partially, autumn. Monthly, an evident influence was played by Q_{Peak} , which resulted in the main driver of sediment fluxes. In this sense, the hysteresis patterns built on the relationships between monthly-averaged Q_{Peak} with monthly-averaged SSL as well as with monthly-averaged BL exhibited clockwise loops, highlighting the alternation of high transport efficiency months and months with evident supply-limited conditions. May expressed high averaged Q_{Peak} accompanied by large average SSL and low BL . This seems to suggest that winter weathering processes more effectively supplied the basin with fine than coarse material. Summer was a period of low discharge and sediment fluxes, i.e., conditions that may have favored sediment replenishment over the catchment. September showed a manifest high transport efficiency that may have been boosted by the sediment availability inherited from the summer but more importantly, is a consequence of September 1994 and the large and infrequent event that occurred in this month, which dictated a wide signal observable also at a monthly scale. Such impact was clearly documented by the double mass curve, analyzing the consistency between cumulated Ru and cumulated TL . Here, September 1994 resulted in an evident breakpoint, inducing a change in the long-term trend. Particularly, it caused about 8 years of intensified sediment conveyance, agreeing with the memory effect documented in the Rio Cordon basin at the event scale. During this period of increased sediment fluxes, monthly BL and SSC_{Peak} were strongly correlated, suggesting how the streambed altered by the September 1994 flood was frequently reworked, by releasing fine material. Therefore, the obtained results emphasized the complex interaction between climatic, hydrological, and sedimentary conditions acting in the alpine basins. Complexity that may be further exacerbated in light of the ongoing climate change. In this sense, this work provided a somewhat better understanding of how alpine basins may respond to large and infrequent events, which will be expected more frequently in the future. Such events, although acting on short time scales, can influence the mountain basins on monthly, seasonal, annual, and decennial scales. For these reasons, it is recommendable to persist in the monitoring at different spatial and temporal scales, permitting the best approach to the climate change effects.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Riccardo Rainato: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original

draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giacomo Pellegrini:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Mario Aristide Lenzi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Lorenzo Picco:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2024.109590>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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